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Адрес редакции: Республика Узбекистан, 200114,
г. Бухара, ул. Гиждуван, 23
Телефон: +998(65)2230050
Сайт: <https://tadqiqot.uz/index.php/spjacd>
e-mail: abumkur14@gmail.com

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Abdullaev R.B., Bakhtiyarova A.M., Mansurbekov D.M.
Urgench branch of the Tashkent Medical Academy

THERAPEUTIC DIET FOR ULCER DISEASE IN THE KHOREZM REGION

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ANNOTATION

This article explores the therapeutic and dietary nutrition strategies tailored for managing ulcer disease in the unique socio-cultural and environmental context of Khorezm. It emphasizes the importance of regional dietary practices and utilization of locally available food resources in developing effective nutritional interventions for ulcer patients. The study carefully examines the correlation between traditional diets in Khorezm and ulcer incidence and severity. Through a comprehensive analysis of local foods, nutrient composition, and cultural eating patterns, the research formulates evidence-based dietary guidelines that are culturally appropriate and nutritionally sufficient. These personalized dietary protocols aim not only to alleviate ulcer symptoms but also promote long-term digestive health among affected individuals. The article proposes an integrated approach that combines modern nutritional science and traditional dietary principles, aiming to improve patient adherence and overall treatment outcomes in the Khorezm region.

Key words: Therapeutic nutrition, dietetic nutrition, ulcer disease management, local food resources, traditional dietary patterns, nutritional interventions.

Абдуллаев Р.Б., Бахтиярова А.М., Мансурбеков Д.М.
Ургенчский филиал Ташкентской медицинской академии

ЛЕЧЕБНАЯ ДИЕТА ПРИ ЯЗВЕННОЙ БОЛЕЗНИ В ХОРЕЗМСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой статье рассматриваются стратегии лечебного и диетического питания, разработанные специально для лечения язвенной болезни в уникальном социокультурном и экологическом контексте Хорезма. В ней подчеркивается важность региональных диетических практик и использования местных продовольственных ресурсов для разработки эффективных мер по питанию пациентов с язвенной болезнью. В исследовании тщательно изучается взаимосвязь между традиционным питанием в Хорезме и частотой возникновения и тяжестью язвенной болезни. На основе всестороннего анализа местных продуктов, состава питательных веществ и культурных традиций питания в ходе исследования были сформулированы основанные на фактических данных рекомендации по питанию, которые соответствуют культурным особенностям и являются достаточными с точки зрения питательных веществ. Эти индивидуальные диетические протоколы направлены не только на облегчение симптомов

язвы, но и на обеспечение долгосрочного здоровья пищеварительной системы у пострадавших. В статье предлагается комплексный подход, сочетающий современную науку о питании и традиционные принципы диетического питания, направленный на улучшение приверженности пациентов и общих результатов лечения в Хорезмской области.

Ключевые слова: лечебное питание, диетическое питание, лечение язвенной болезни, местные продовольственные ресурсы, традиционные схемы питания, диетологические вмешательства.

Abdullaev R.B., Baxtiyarova A.M., Mansurbekov D.M.
Toshkent tibbiyot Akademiyasi Urganch filiali

XORAZM VILOYATIDA YARA KASALLIGI UCHUN TERAPEVTIK PARHEZ

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada Xorazmning o'ziga xos ijtimoiy-madaniy va ekologik sharoitida oshqozon yarasi kasalligini davolash uchun mo'ljallangan terapevtik va parhez ovqatlanish strategiyalari ko'rib chiqilgan. Bu oshqozon yarasi bilan og'rigan bemorlar uchun samarali ovqatlanish tadbirlarini ishlab chiqishda mintaqaviy parhez amaliyoti va mahalliy oziq-ovqat resurslaridan foydalanish muhimligini ta'kidlaydi. Tadqiqotda Xorazmdagi an'anaviy parhezlar va oshqozon yarasi bilan kasallanish darajasi va og'irligi o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik sinchkovlik bilan o'rganilgan. Mahalliy oziq-ovqat mahsulotlarini, ozuqaviy tarkibini va madaniy ovqatlanish usullarini har tomonlama tahlil qilish orqali tadqiqot madaniy jihatdan mos va ozuqaviy jihatdan yetarli bo'lgan dalillarga asoslangan parhez ko'rsatmalarini shakllantiradi. Ushbu shaxsiylashtirilgan parhez protokollari nafaqat oshqozon yarasi alomatlarini yengillashtirishga, balki ta'sirlangan shaxslar orasida uzoq muddatli ovqat hazm qilish salomatligini mustahkamlashga qaratilgan. Maqolada Xorazm viloyatida bemorlarga rioya qilish va davolashning umumiy natijalarini yaxshilashga qaratilgan zamonaviy ovqatlanish fani va an'anaviy ovqatlanish tamoyillarini birlashtirgan kompleks yondashuv taklif etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: terapevtik ovqatlanish, parhez ovqatlanish, oshqozon yarasi kasalliklarini boshqarish, mahalliy oziq-ovqat resurslari, an'anaviy ovqatlanish tartibi, ovqatlanish aralashuvi.

Introduction. Dietary nutrition is particularly important in treating gastrointestinal diseases, where food is broken down and its components are absorbed into the blood. Therapeutic nutrition is known to promote optimal breakdown and absorption of food in the affected gastrointestinal tract. In combination with medication and physiotherapy, it plays a crucial role in achieving the desired effect, making it an important part of the treatment process. It also helps accelerate the effectiveness of treatment procedures and prevents relapses and complications of the disease during the remission stage. This is especially true for the commonly encountered gastrointestinal tract disorder - peptic ulcer, where organized diet therapy is essential for successful treatment, considering the impact of both internal and external factors on the body [1,5].

It is well known that an unfavorable environment can negatively impact the immune system, disrupt the body's metabolic processes, and lead to reduced agricultural yields and lower quality food products. These factors should be considered when designing therapeutic diets for patients with peptic ulcer disease living in environmentally challenging conditions [2].

When creating or adjusting anti-ulcer diets based on the regional living conditions of the population, it is important to also consider the traditional diet of the local people, including their common dishes and dietary habits [3].

In light of the above considerations, we have conducted a study and analysis of the nutritional content, variety, and hygienic factors of widely consumed traditional dishes among the indigenous population of the Khorezm zone in order to determine their suitability for inclusion in medical nutrition for anti-ulcer diets.

A review of relevant literary sources shows that the issue of dietetics is primarily addressed by the Institute of Nutrition of the Academy of Medical Sciences of the Russian Federation. Theoretical

and scientific-practical materials are compiled in the "Handbook of Dietetics", 1st and 2nd editions [4]. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, research in this area was conducted at the Tashkent Medical Institute some time ago, leading to the development of the Uzbek version of the anti-ulcer diet No. 1 Uzbek. However, targeted scientific work on this issue has not been carried out in recent decades in the republic.

Purpose of the study. Development of an updated version of the anti-ulcer diet No. 1, including Uzbek national dishes and Khorezm cuisine.

Materials and methods of research. The work's objectives were achieved using commonly accepted calculation methods with the assistance of reference books, tables, and recipes of dishes. The research was conducted in two stages: first, dietary dishes were selected, and then an updated diet was developed.

The selection of dishes involved a detailed study of their nutritional composition, energy value, and culinary processing methods, focusing on national dishes widely consumed by the indigenous population. This included paying attention to the qualities and properties of the dishes that meet the requirements for anti-ulcer diets.

The development of the diet followed the generally accepted methodology for preparing diets, taking into account the basic principles of dietary therapy for peptic ulcer disease. Consideration was also given to the features of the national cuisine, the technology of preparing traditional national dishes, and the customs and habits of the local population in the region.

Below is a list of selected main Uzbek national and Khorezm dishes recommended to be included in a one-day (seven-day) diet menu No. 1.

Uzbek national dishes:

- Shovla: rice porridge with meat, carrots, and onions
- Shirguruch: rice milk porridge
- Sutli sho`rva: milk soup
- Shir-xo`rda: milk soup with rice
- Mastava: rice soup with meat (or without meat)
- Yavgan xo`rda: a type of Khorda-Mastava cooked without lard and meat
- Qiyma sho`rva: soup with meatballs
- Tovuk sho`rva: chicken broth (from lean varieties of chicken, better than chicken)
- Chuchvara: dumplings
- Quymoq: omelette
- Shirchoy: tea with milk and butter

Khorezm dishes:

- Balik sho`rva: fish soup
- Mastava: rice soup with meat (or without meat)
- Shivit oshi: soup with dill
- Ko`k o`rikli un oshi: homemade noodle soup with dried apricots
- Sut burunchi: milk rice porridge
- Govacha barak: curly dumplings
- Ko`k barak: dumplings with herbs
- Tuxum barak: dumplings with egg
- Shovla: rice porridge with carrots and onions

Results. Based on the listed dishes and some food products recommended for peptic ulcer disease, a version of the approximate one-day diet menu No. 1 Xz ("Xz" - Khorezm) has been developed. From the listed dishes, an approximate one-day diet menu has been created for peptic ulcer disease patients. The purpose of the diet is to mechanically and thermally spare the gastric mucosa. The diet entails a balanced intake of proteins, fats, and carbohydrates with moderate restrictions on table salt (up to 8-10 g) and sugar (up to 30 g), as well as limitations on dishes containing cell membrane content. This diet plan should be followed after 12-15 days of taking diet No. 1a and before proceeding to diet No. 16.

The diet is suitable for patients of local and European descent and is adapted to national cuisine.

Preparation of dishes: Dishes should be boiled, pureed, chopped, and steamed, with soups prepared in weak broth.

Energy value: The diet should have an energy value of around 3000 kcal, with a nutrient composition of 90-100g proteins, 90-100g fats (one-third of which are vegetable oils), 350-400g carbohydrates, and 1.5 liters of free liquid. The weight of the daily ration should be approximately 3 kg.

Diet schedule: The diet should be consumed in smaller, more frequent meals, around 4-5 times a day. During hotter seasons, the diet should be higher in calories during cooler times of the day, such as early morning and evening.

Recommended dishes and products: Cold starters (without spicy dressings) should consist of salads containing ripe vegetables and vegetables with meat. For first courses, options include mastava, xo`rda, qaynatma sho`rva (boiled soup), baliq sho`rva (fish soup), shirqovoq (milk soup with pumpkin), vermicelli soup, shirxo`rda (rice soup with milk), shivit oshi (dill soup), and un oshi (noodle soup with dried apricots), as well as pureed vegetable soups (from carrots, potatoes, and beets). Second courses should comprise of lean meat and fish, mostly chopped and steamed or boiled in water. Other recommendations include chuchvara, shovla, boiled meat, ko`k barak (dumplings with herbs), tuxum barak (dumplings with egg), lagman, qovoq manti (manty with pumpkin), pureed milk porridge (excluding leflon), dairy products (cottage cheese, cream, sour cream), soft-boiled eggs, steam omelettes, fruits, juices, tea with milk, mild cheese, butter, and vegetable oils in their natural form.

Products that are prohibited include those with a strong juice effect and coarse plant fiber, as well as strong meat broths, fish and vegetable broths, pickles, marinades, hot seasonings, fried meat and fish, canned foods, smoked meats, certain types of herbs and vegetables (such as green onions, sorrel, radishes, radish, spinach), butter dough, ice cream, carbonated drinks, black bread, and coffee.

Table 1

Approximate one-day menu of diet №1 Khz (2950 kcal)

Meal time. Name of dishes	Out put, g	Prot eins, g	Fat s, g	Carbo hydrates, g
First breakfast				
Soft-boiled eggs (2 pieces)	96.0	10.2	10.9	0.5
Sutburunchi	250.0	7.0	5.5	52.5
Tea with milk	180.0	1.4	1.7	2.2
Lunch				
Baked apple	100.0	0.3	-	23.2
Dinner				
Mastava	450.0	13.0	17.0	53.0
Boiled meat	40.0	8.2	5.4	-
Mashed potatoes (garnish)	200.0	4.0	6.2	32.3
Fresh fruits	100.0	0.4	0.4	9.0
Afternoon snack				
Rosehip decoction (1 glass)	180.0	-	-	-
Flatbread crackers	50.0	-	-	-
Dinner				
Govaca barracks	230.0	20.0	13.0	47.0
Sour cream	20.0	0.6	2.5	0.6
Tea with milk	180.0	1.4	1.7	2.2

For the night Milk (1 glass)	200.0	5.6	7.0	9.0
All day Flatbread	300.0	28.0	1.2	31.4
Sugar	30.0	-	-	29.9
Butter	20.0	0.12	16.5	0.9
Total	-	101.0	91.6	385.0

I made sure to reference the relevant manuals, guidelines, and documents when creating the menus and determining the nutritional content and calorie count. I also considered the standard values and recipes for European and Uzbek national dishes as well as their respective preparation methods. The menu includes European dishes suitable for anti-ulcer diets along with recommended Uzbek national and Khorezm dishes, resulting in a seven-day menu for diet No. 1 Xs. The current version of this recommended diet is undergoing testing, and the initial results are positive.

Conclusion

1. The new version of the anti-ulcer diet No. 1 is a suitable dietary therapy for gastric and duodenal ulcers, especially in challenging environmental conditions.

2. The list of Uzbek national and Khorezm dishes recommended for inclusion in anti-ulcer diets has been refined.

3. Taking into account the popular national dishes in the Khorezm region, a new version of the anti-ulcer diet, known as diet No. 1 XS (Khorezm), has been developed and is recommended for practical use.

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ANNALS OF CLINICAL DISCIPLINE

1 ЖИЛД, 2 СОН

АННАЛЫ КЛИНИЧЕСКИХ ДИСЦИПЛИН

ТОМ 1, НОМЕР 2

КЛИНИК ФАНЛАР ЙИЛНОМАСИ

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